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Addressing the Works of World Literature with Radio Play Application

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Abstract

In the study, within the scope of World Literature course, radio play adaptations of works from French and Russian literatures were vocalized by pre-service teachers and tried to be presented in radio play format. In this regard, the aim of the research is to address the attitudes of pre-service teachers who experience preparing radio plays towards collaborative studies and their perception of information communication technologies competence levels. In addition, the thoughts of pre-service teachers about whether they enjoy the work of preparing radio plays, vocalizing, getting to know the work closely, and getting to know the author closely were also discussed. It is thought that the research will contribute to getting to know the literary work, the author and the characteristics of the period in which it emerged through radio plays, learning by doing and experiencing, learning permanently and with pleasure, increasing motivation and contributing to speaking skills. Because in today's education and training environments, rather than transferring knowledge, students are expected to be involved in the education and training process in which they are active, access information in creative ways, construct knowledge, learn collaboratively and interactively. In the study, qualitative and quantitative data were collected and mixed method was used. The study group of the research consists of pre-service teachers taking the World Literature course. "Cooperative Learning Scale" and "Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) Competence Perception Scale" were used as data collection tools. The findings obtained as a result of the research indicate that pre-service teachers' perceptions of collaborative studies for preparing radio plays are at a "high" level; their mean scores of ICT competence perception are at a "sufficient" level; there is no significant difference in their attitudes towards collaborative learning and their perceptions of competence in using ICT according to gender. Most of the pre-service teachers stated that it was their first time doing such an application. Regarding the qualitative findings, the students stated that they enjoyed the radio play very much, that this application contributed to them to get to know the work closely, that they had the opportunity to get to know the work more closely, and that they were curious about the other works and life of the author. More students stated that going beyond just knowing the work as a name and giving life to a character in the work ensured the permanence of the work and what was learned. They also stated that they learned about new applications related to technology through the radio play they experienced and that they saw their deficiencies related to technology.

Keywords: Radio Play, World Literature, Text Vocalization, Collaborative Studies, Teacher Candidates

1. Introduction

Radio is still an important broadcasting medium today, and radio plays are an important part of radio that entertains and informs people and allows them to have a good time. "The first regular broadcast in Turkey started on May 6, 1972 on Istanbul radio. After a while, Ankara Radio started broadcasting. As in the rest of the world, radios were broadcasting theater plays during the Representation Hour" (Duruel, 2014: 57). Although Lord Asa Briggs said that some of Shakespeare's classics were broadcast on the BBC on February 16, 1923, it is generally accepted that British dramatist Richard Hugs' *A Comedy of Danger*, broadcast on January 15, 1924, was the first radio play (Özden, 1997: 7).

Radio plays are a field intertwined with literature. Radio plays, like works of literature, develop the imagination. It offers its readers and listeners, whom it addresses not visually but visually, opportunities such as imagining the heroes, events and places in the work, enriching their world, getting to know even unread works closely, empathizing, and meeting new people. As Özdemir (2017) states, "Literature enriches the world of imagination. The events and people in novels come alive in our minds. Radio theater is closer to the novel. When listening to radio theater, it is as if you have lived the event. It is an art of speech and sound that requires mastery of sound art in terms of the use of sound as a field with artistic value and cultural value" (p. 9-10). Radio play is a field that makes important contributions to cultural life. It would be a different practice for students who are not accustomed to the traditional and only appealing to the ear and who are familiar with new media tools to get to know the work closely in an educational environment and to use it in a way that contributes to the development of verbal communication skills. In the literature, studies aiming to show the usability of radio plays in the development of verbal communication skills have been carried out, albeit to a lesser extent. It is possible that radio plays can be used to develop listening and speaking skills in courses such as Turkish and literature where verbal communication is predominant. In the special field competencies of teachers adopted by the Ministry of National Education in 2011, the article "developing students' critical and creative thinking, decision-making and problem solving skills" was included. Developing technology and changing social structure necessitates critical reading, thinking, using information and communication technologies (ICT) and a perspective in this direction. Therefore, it is a necessity of our age that pre-service teachers studying in faculties of education develop their attitudes towards critical and creative thinking, communication, problem solving, research, decision making and using information technologies in a positive way and incorporate technology into their lessons. Through radio plays, works of Turkish literature, works of world literature, works of children's literature are learned, known and recognized by large masses.

The aim of the study is to examine the attitudes towards collaborative studies and the levels of information communication technologies competence perceptions of pre-service teachers who experience preparing radio plays. In addition, pre-service teachers' thoughts about preparing a radio play (vocalization, getting to know the author and the work closely) were also discussed. For this purpose, the following questions will be tried to be answered in the study.

1. At what level are the attitudes of pre-service teachers who experience preparing a radio play towards cooperative learning?
2. What is the level of pre-service teachers' perceptions of competence in using Information Communication Technologies (ICT)?
3. Is there a significant difference between pre-service teachers' attitudes towards cooperative learning and their perceptions of competence in using information communication technologies (ICT) according to gender?
4. Write your thoughts about the contributions or negativities of the radio play to you under the headings below:
 - a) Enjoying the work done
 - b) On vocalization/speaking
 - c) To get to know the work closely
 - d) To get to know the author closely

2. Method

In this section, information about the purpose, importance, model, study group, data collection and analysis of the study is given.

2.1 Research Model

In the study, mixed method was used, which integrates the results of the research by using quantitative and qualitative data collection methods together. The purpose of using qualitative and quantitative research methods together in the same study is to increase the advantages and decrease the disadvantages of qualitative and quantitative research (Creswell, 2003).

2.2 Study Group

The research was conducted with sixty pre-service teachers from the Faculty of Education who took the World Literature course and answered the survey questions completely.

2.3 Data Collection Tools

Quantitative and qualitative data were collected in the study. "Personal Information Form", "Cooperative Learning Scale" developed by Kiper (2016), "Information and Communication Technologies Competence Perception Scale for Prospective Teachers" developed by Şad and Nalçacı (2015) were used to collect quantitative data.

2.3.1 Quantitative Data Collection Tools

2.3.1.1 Cooperative Learning Scale

The "Cooperative Learning Scale" developed by Kiper (2016) consists of 20 items. Of these 20 items, 11 are positive and 9 are negative. In the evaluation of the positive items, "Strongly Agree" (5), "Agree" (4), "Undecided" (3), "Disagree" (2), "Strongly Disagree" (1), while in the evaluation of the negative items, a five-point Likert-type scale with "Strongly Agree" (1), "Agree" (2), "Undecided" (3), "Disagree" (4), "Strongly Disagree" (5) points was used. Cronbach Alpha coefficient was calculated to reveal the reliability of the scale. The Cronbach Alpha value of the scale was calculated as 0.924.

2.3.1.2 Information and Communication Technologies Competence Perception Scale for Prospective Teachers

Another scale used in the study is the scale developed by Şad and Nalçacı (2015) Prospective Teachers' Perceived Competencies about Integrating Information and Communication Technologies into Education. The scale form is organized in likert format with 5-point scale ranging from 'I am quite competent' to 'I am quite inadequate'. In order to reveal the reliability of the scale, Cronbach Alpha coefficient was calculated. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient of the scale was found to be ,964. The scale consists of 30 items.

2.3.2 Qualitative Data Collection Tools

2.3.2.1 Semi-structured Interview Form

Within the scope of the qualitative dimension of the research, the thoughts of the pre-service teachers who experienced preparing a radio play about enjoying the work, vocalizing, getting to know the author and the work closely were discussed. For this purpose, a semi-structured interview form consisting of four open-ended questions was prepared by the researcher. In order to ensure the internal validity of these questions, the opinions of field experts who completed their doctorate in the field of Turkish Language Literature Education were taken. The semi-structured interview questions asked to the prospective teachers are as follows:

1. Write your thoughts about the contributions or negativities of the radio play to you under the headings below.
 - a) In terms of enjoying the work done
 - b) On vocalization/speaking
 - c) To get to know the work closely
 - d) To get to know the author closely

2.4. Data Analysis

The quantitative data obtained in the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as percentage, frequency and arithmetic mean; qualitative data were analyzed using content analysis. With content analysis, it is tried to define the data and to reveal the facts that may be hidden in the data. The basic process in content analysis is to bring together similar data within the framework of certain concepts and themes and to organize and interpret them (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2006). The Kolmogorov Smirnov test was used to check whether the numerical variables were normally distributed. The data show normal distribution.

2.5 Radio Play Implementation and Planning

In the study, radio play adaptations of works from French and Russian literatures are discussed within the scope of world literature. These play adaptations given below were vocalized by the students within the scope of the World Literature course and tried to be presented in radio play format.

Radio Play Adaptations and Responsible Works:

Group 1: The Little Prince adapted from Antoine de Saint-Exupery's work of the same name

Group 2: The Inspector based on N.Gogol's work of the same name

Group 3: A.Chekhov's play The Wedding

Group 4: A.Chekhov's Anniversary Celebration was distributed to the groups according to the class size, with a narrator and the people in the work.

The weekly practices carried out during a lesson period are given below.

2.6 Process and Implementation

Week 1 (14.02.2022) Teacher candidates were informed about the content of the study. Information about the radio play, adapted works, radio play-literature relationship was given.

Week 2 (21.02.2022) Radio play, the period of radio plays to be discussed, works, radio play-literature relationship continued to be explained. Information about the radio play was given and its relationship with verbal communication was mentioned.

Week 3 (28.03.2022) The works and the number of people to be performed by the teacher candidates were determined and the subjects were distributed to the class. The prospective teachers were asked to share their roles and read the works.

Week 4 (07.03.2022) Technical information about the realization of the radio play, programs related to vocalization, sound editing, etc. Sample radio plays were sent to prospective teachers.

Week 5 (14.03.2022) Teacher candidates came together and started rehearsals.

Week 6 (21.03.2022) Teacher candidates listened to the radio play samples sent to them and made evaluations by getting to know the work they were responsible for more closely.

Week 7 (28.03.2022) Teacher candidates came together and continued to read and rehearse.

Week 8 (04.04.2022) Sources for the works they used in their studies were sent.

Week 9-10 (11.04.2022-18.04.2022) Teacher candidates continued to read and rehearse together.

11.-12.Week (25.04.2022-02.05.2022) The prospective teachers were asked to follow the plays of their other groupmates.

13.-14.Week: (09.05.2022-16.05.2022) The prospective teachers' radio plays were analyzed and evaluated.

3. Findings And Interpretation

In this section, the findings related to pre-service teachers' perceptions of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) competence and Cooperative Learning Attitude levels are presented.

3.1 Findings Related to Quantitative Data

Table 1: Normal distribution values for total scores of cooperative learning scale, information and communication technologies (ict) competence perception scale

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Skewness	Kurtosis
	Statistics	Sd	p		
Cooperative Learning Scale	0,10	60,00	0,18	-0,63	1,15
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) Competence Perception Scale	0,07	60,00	0,20	-0,14	-0,53

In order to determine the analyses to be selected to test the hypotheses, it was checked whether the data were suitable for normal distribution. The data obtained from the Shapiro-Wilk normality tests with a significance level greater than 0.05 showed a normal distribution, and the kurtosis and skewness values were between ± 2.0 (George & Mallery, 2010) and the values did not deviate excessively from the normal distribution.

In order to answer the first problem of the study, "What is the level of the attitudes of the pre-service teachers who realized the radio application towards cooperative learning?", the results of the total scores and descriptive statistics of the pre-service teachers are shown in Table 2 and Table 3:

Table 2: Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values of prospective teachers' attitude scores towards cooperative learning

	N	Min	Maks.	Average	Standard Deviation
Cooperative Learning Scale	60,00	33,00	96,00	71,12	12,38

According to the results in Table 2, the mean score of the pre-service teachers on the cooperative learning scale is 71.12, the standard deviation is 12.38, the highest score is 96, and the lowest score is 33. In order to determine the level of participation from the scores obtained from the scales, the group width value was evaluated using the formula $4/5=0.80$. For this purpose; 1.00-1.80 was taken as "very low level"; 1.80-2.60 as "low level"; 2.60-3.40 as "medium level"; 3.40-4.20 as "high level"; 4.20-5 as "very high level". The result of the division of the total score of the pre-service teachers by the number of items is 3.55 and it can be said that their attitudes towards cooperative learning are at "high" level.

Table 3: Descriptive results of cooperative learning levels for prospective teachers

	Level	n	%
Cooperative Learning Scale	Strongly disagree	1	1,7
	Disagree	3	5,0
	Undecided	19	31,7
	I agree	31	51,7
	Absolutely agree	6	10,0

According to the mean scores obtained from the cooperative learning scale, 51.7% (n:31) of the pre-service teachers were at the "agree" level and 31.7% (n:19) were at the "undecided" level.

In order to answer the second problem of the study, "What is the level of pre-service teachers' perceptions of competence in using Information Communication Technologies (ICT)?", the total scores and descriptive statistics of the pre-service teachers were calculated. The related results are shown in Table 4 and Table 5.

Table 4: Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values of preservice teachers' perceptions of competence in using information communication technologies (ict)

	N	Min	Maks.	Average	Standard Deviation
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) Competence Perception Scale for Prospective Teachers	60,00	88,00	149,00	120,41	16,24

The average total score of the ICT competence perception scale for pre-service teachers was 120.41 ± 16.24 , with a minimum score of 88 and a maximum score of 149.

In order to determine the level of participation from the scores obtained from the scales, the group width value was evaluated using the formula $4/5 = .80$. For this purpose; 1.00-1.80 was taken as "very low level"; 1.80-2.60 as "low level"; 2.60-3.40 as "medium level"; 3.40-4.20 as "sufficient level"; 4.20-5 as "quite sufficient level". It can be said that pre-service teachers' perceptions of competence in using Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) are at the "sufficient" level with the result 4 related to the number of items divided by the total score.

Table 5: Descriptive results of information and communication technologies competency levels for prospective teachers

	Level	N	%
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) Competence Perception Scale for Prospective Teachers	Undecided	10	16,9
	I agree	29	49,2
	Strongly agree	21	33,9

In Table 5, the perception levels of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) competence of pre-service teachers are shown as follows: 49,2% of them are adequate, 16,9% of them are partially adequate, 33,9% of them are quite adequate.

According to the mean scores obtained from the Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) competence perception scale for pre-service teachers, it was determined that 49,2% (n:29) of the pre-service teachers were at the level of "agree" and 33,9% (n:20) were at the level of "strongly agree".

In order to answer the third problem of the study, "Is there a significant difference between the attitudes of the pre-service teachers who realized the radio application towards cooperative learning and their perceptions of competence in using information communication technologies (ICT) according to gender?", the total scores and descriptive statistics of the pre-service teachers were calculated. Related results are shown in Table 8.

Table 6: Comparison of cooperative learning and information and communication technologies (ict) competency levels by gender

	Gender	n	$\bar{X} \pm SS$	t	sd	p
Cooperative Learning Scale	Male	11	3,74 $\pm$ 0,40	1,07	58	0,29
	Woman	49	3,52 $\pm$ 0,65			

Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) Competence Perception Scale for Prospective Teachers	Male	11	4,09±0,52	0,54	57	0,59
	Woman	49	4,00±0,55			

As seen in Table 6, the scores of pre-service teachers' cooperative learning attitude, information and communication technologies scale do not show a statistically significant difference according to gender ($p>0.05$).

3.2 Findings Related to Qualitative Data

The findings obtained as a result of analyzing the radio plays put forward by the pre-service teachers with the content analysis method are given below.

1. *Fifty-seven pre-service teachers stated that they enjoyed the work and had a lot of fun with the question "whether they enjoyed the work":* Examples of these students' thoughts are as follows:

Table 7: Did you enjoy the radio play application? Answers Related to the Question

Whether you enjoy the work or not	f
Yes, I enjoyed it.	57
No, I did not enjoy it.	1
Partially enjoyed it.	2

a. In addition to the difficulty of working as a group, i.e. collaboratively, there were students who stated that it was enjoyable to work in unity and solidarity to produce a good product:

- It was very nice to do a collaborative work. I had the opportunity to get to know people I did not know in the class. S4
- I had never done such a study before. For this reason, we carried out the study with great pleasure. In addition, this study gave us the opportunity to spend a pleasant time with the people in the group. S7
- It was a lot of fun to perform the book as a group. It was a very different experience for us to listen to the latest version of the book from different voices. S14
- I enjoyed it. I understood the importance of cooperation better. I enjoyed giving the emotions of the character. S21
- I enjoyed it. I found that we would improve ourselves at every moment of the process, including the parts I read. I also had the opportunity to further develop my sense of responsibility through cooperative work. S23

b. The opinions of those who stated that new information about record organization and technology was useful and exciting are as follows:

- I enjoyed it. I learned new sites and applications that I can use in the future. It was fun to prepare. S48
- Yes, it was fun. Since I am very good with the computer and I like it very much, the recording editing part was good for me. S56

c. The opinions of the students who stated that it was enjoyable to feel those emotions and empathize with them by taking on other roles and therefore enjoyed the practice:

- It was a very enjoyable work. It was very fun to feel and vocalize by getting into other roles. I couldn't help thinking that I wish I had such a profession. S5
- I really enjoyed the radio play work we did. When we read our comedy play on our own, it didn't seem funny, I wasn't very impressed. We had a lot of fun recording it when we performed it. We couldn't stop laughing most of the time, especially when there were sound effects. S8
- Yes, I bought it. It was very enjoyable for me to take part in a play by Gogol, one of the masters of World Literature, especially playing the role of Andreyevna, the wife of the inspector. S27

- Yes, it is. It was a different and beautiful study. S29

d. The views of the student who stated that he partially enjoyed the study:

- Since it was quite difficult to gather the group, frankly, it was not a process that I enjoyed too much. However, the application part was quite fun. No one wanted to make sacrifices in the first process, which frankly cooled me down against the homework. S20
- I partly enjoyed this work I did because it was a tiring work, but on the other hand, we produced a fun and different work product with my group. While voicing or listening to the Inspector play, I witnessed that the characters in the content of the book were ridiculous and the humorous aspects of the events were skillfully handled. Especially the dialogues of the character who deceived the officers disguised as an inspector were enjoyable and gripping. S40

e. The opinions of the students who stated that it was very enjoyable to present a favorite book as a radio play:

- Yes, I did. It was very nice to revive my favorite book. S47
- Yes, I had a lot of fun doing our work. I especially enjoyed doing the audio theater of a book I love. I also played the flower as a character. The sentences of this character affected me a lot when I read the book. Therefore, it was a pleasant work for me. S59

f. The opinions of the students who stated that doing such a study for the first time and using their voices was an exciting and enjoyable practice are as follows:

- I enjoyed it. It was enjoyable for me to reflect and vocalize the emotional states of the characters. S15
- Yes, because it was a nice aspect to feel like a hero of the book. Being like living that moment during the vocalization stage was my favorite stage. S17
- Yes, I had a great pleasure in our radio play work, because The Little Prince is a very well-known and admired work. It was very enjoyable for me to voice a character from such a beautiful work.
- Yes, I enjoyed the work we did. I enjoyed the vocalization part the most. Because we tried to give the emotion in that part. S26

2. Did vocalization/speaking give you pleasure? Why? In what ways did you feel incomplete or comfortable?

Five students gave negative answers to the question and four students gave partial answers. The students who expressed that they enjoyed the study expressed that they sometimes experienced uneasiness about getting stuck and making the wrong vocalization.

Table 8: Did you enjoy voiceover in the radio play application? Why? In which ways did you feel incomplete or comfortable?

Did vocalization/speaking give you pleasure? Why? In which ways did you feel incomplete or comfortable?	F
Yes	51
Partially	4
No. I had a hard time	5

a. The opinions of the students who stated that they enjoyed it are as follows:

- I enjoyed it very much. I am already successful in such activities. I believe that I enter the role well and reflect it both vocally and physically. S4
- It gave me pleasure. The point where I felt incomplete was portraying a male character. But in general, it was an enjoyable job. S49
- Yes, it was quite enjoyable. Especially vocalization made me feel like I was in the play. In my first vocalization experience, I was afraid of not being able to integrate with the character in the work and not reflecting that emotion. S57

b. Opinions of the student who stated that he/she partially enjoyed it:

- I can say that I partially enjoyed it. I tried to give emotion in the parts where I had dialogues. And it was little hard. S22

3. Did the radio play practice contribute to getting to know the author's work closely? In which ways? Did the radio play application contribute to getting to know the author's work closely? In which ways? In response to the question, the majority of the students stated that they got to know the work more closely and in depth. The opinions regarding this are as follows:

Table 9: Did the radio play application contribute to getting to know the author's work closely? In which ways?

Answers to the question

Did the radio play application contribute to getting to know the author's work closely? In which ways?	F
Yes, it did.	56
Partially provided.	2
No it did not.	2

a. Some of the opinions of the students who stated that they understood the work better and that it was better memorized because they vocalized it are as follows:

- I became curious about Anton Chekhov's other works. It awakened the desire to research Russian literature and contributed a lot to me. I had the opportunity to learn who is in Russian literature, which works were written, and what kind of path literature followed in Russia at that time. S4
- I was very happy to have the opportunity to meet the piece. Since we performed this piece, I think that the piece has a very special place in my mind and heart. S7
- "The Anniversary Celebration" was the first work of Anton Chekhov I ever read. I never laughed when I read it, but I laughed so much when my friends acted it out that the sound recording was disrupted because of me. If I had read this work as a plain text, I would not have enjoyed it. With the radio play application, I discovered that it has funny sides. S8

b. The opinions of the students who stated that they had left the work unfinished or had not read it before and that they had information about the work with this radio play application are as follows:

- Yes, it contributed. Because although I had knowledge about the work, I had not had the opportunity to read the work from beginning to end. S16
- Of course they contributed to getting to know the work. With the radio play we prepared, I think it became impossible to forget the work, its fiction and its characters. S28

c. The opinions of the students who stated that they reached a certain idea about the language and style of the work are as follows:

- I think I have more permanent knowledge about the style of Anton Chekhov's plays. S2
- Of course it did. It allowed us to get to know the author's style and feelings closely. S21

d. The opinions of the students who stated that they understood the characters in the work better are as follows:

- Yes, it provided this opportunity. First of all, the explanations about the characters in the work helped me to get to know the characters more clearly and thus to make sense of the character's behavior and words more easily throughout the work. S29
- I had the opportunity to examine the work better. It enabled me to analyze the characters in the work better. S47
- Yes, I was able to have an idea about how he constructed the characters and I was able to understand the author's imagination with the help of the voiceover.

4. Did the radio play application contribute to getting to know the author better? In which ways? Answers to the question

Table 10: Did the radio play application contribute to getting to know the author better? In which ways?

Did the radio play application contribute to getting to know the author better? In which ways?	F
Yes it did.	40

Partially provided.	12
No it did not.	8

The statements of the students who stated that they did research on his life and other works are as follows:

- Yes, definitely. I can say that Chekhov managed to be the writer who interested me the most. It is impressive that he is the greatest short story writer besides his identity as a physician. His stories and plays are quite beautiful. In addition to his numerical intelligence, I was very impressed by his verbal success and his interest in literature. S4
- In the course of the course, we talked about the humorous criticism of Gogol. However, it was not possible for me to witness this aspect of the author without reading a work completely. I could not get to know the author closely, but I felt some aspects I knew about the author more clearly in his writing. S30
- I found out that the author was a pilot and a French citizen and that he wrote works such as Night Flight S41
- Yes, it did. Because I also tried to research and learn about the author of the book we were vocalizing. In addition, the work written by the author and the style of the work gave us a clue about many features of the author. S58

4. Conclusion

Today, developing technology, new communication technologies and media tools are important in education as in all fields. Technology and new media tools replace traditional and classical methods in education. Sometimes traditional and outdated practices can be revived and made functional with new technology and media tools. As a matter of fact, as Göçer and Kurt (2020) reported in their study, "It is seen that radio play recordings are available on different platforms such as Spotify, SoundCloud, YouTube Music, radio plays are vocalized and continued in accordance with today's technologies.

In the study, pre-service teachers carried out an application to get to know the adapted works of world literature closely by working collaboratively, using technology, and using verbal communication skills through a radio play. There are various studies on radio plays in the literature. For example, Cankaya (2011) in his study titled "A disappearing broadcast format: Radio drama", Cankaya (2011) discussed the reasons for the disappearance of this type of radio program in Turkey and made evaluations about it. Ayvaz (2016), in his study titled "Behçet Necatigil and Radio Plays", gives information about the characteristics of radio plays and Behçet Necatigil, one of the important names of this genre and radio plays. Karadağ (1976), in his study titled "Radio Theater Education", mentioned the stages of the radio play and provided information about it. Doğan (2007), in his study titled "Changing radio listening habits in Turkey and radio theater in private radios", examined radio play broadcasts. These studies can be multiplied. However, within the scope of our study, it would be more appropriate to look at the studies on the inclusion of radio plays in education. In the literature, there are few studies on the use of radio plays in education. The first of these is a theoretical study conducted by Göçer and Kurt (2020), "The Theoretical study on the use of radio plays in the development of verbal communication skills". In addition, Miçooğulları (2021), "Listening Skills in Teaching Turkish to Foreigners: TRT Dinle and Radio Dramas as Authentic Materials", radio theater was played as an activity to improve the listening skills of foreign students learning Turkish.

The results obtained from the radio play application, which is the subject of this study conducted by pre-service teachers, indicate that pre-service teachers' perceptions of collaborative work for preparing a radio play are at a "high" level, and the mean scores of information and communication technologies competence perception for pre-service teachers are at a "sufficient" level. It can also be said that there is no significant difference between their attitudes towards cooperative learning and their perceptions of competence in using information communication technologies (ICT) according to gender. Most of the pre-service teachers stated that they were doing such an application for the first time. Regarding the qualitative findings, the students stated that they enjoyed the radio play very much, that this application contributed to them in getting to know the work closely,

that they had the opportunity to get to know the work more closely, and that they were curious about the author's other works and life. More students stated that going beyond just knowing the work as a name and giving life to a character in the work ensured the permanence of the work and what was learned. They also stated that they learned about new applications related to technology through the radio play they experienced and that they saw their deficiencies related to technology.

As in this study, the practices and activities to be carried out for collaborative work, the use of technology, and the development of verbal communication skills in lessons aimed at getting to know literary works and the period closely attract the attention of students at all levels of education and make learning enjoyable. Studies similar to these practices can be carried out at all levels of education.

Ethics Committee Permission

The data collection tools were submitted to the Ethics Committee of Kütahya Dumlupınar University and it was stated that the study was in compliance with research and publication ethics with the decision presented below:

Board name = Kütahya Dumlupınar University Rectorate, Social and Human Sciences Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee

Date of decision= 15.02.2022

Document number number= E.78513

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